

**BUSITEMA
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**DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN SMALL TOWNS OF SCENIC AREAS OF UGANDA
A CASE STUDY OF SANGA (C) WARD, SANGA TOWN COUNCIL, KIRUHURA DISTRICT
NEAR
LAKE MBURO NATIONAL PARK**

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**A RESEARCH REPORT SUBMITTED TO FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT
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REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF A
BACHELORS DEGREE IN TOURISM
AND TRAVEL MANAGEMENT
BUSITEMA UNIVESIRTY**

AUGUST, 2024

DECLARATION

DECLARATION

I **KUSASIRA EMMANUEL** hereby declare that the work in this research proposal is original and has never been published or submitted to any institution of learning for any academic award.

Kusasira Emmanuel

BU/UG/2021/3404

Signature..... *Kusasira Emmanuel*

Date..... *27th August, 2024* .

APPROVAL

APPROVAL

This research proposal titled, "*Development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas of Uganda*" has been developed under my supervision and is ready for submission for the award of a Degree of Bachelors of tourism and travel management of Busitema University

Signed: Date: *27/Dec/2024*

Mr. ORINGO JONAH
(Supervisor)

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my family members; mostly my parents (Mr. Tumushabe colleb and Mrs. Jennifer Kishokye) and my brother Nuwataho Hannington for each and every effort they have put in place both spiritually and financially to make me who I am today. May almighty God bless you and lift you on high forever endeavors.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Short form	Meaning
EAC	East African community
GDP	Growth domestic product
UWA	Uganda wildlife authority
MTWA	Ministry of tourism, wildlife and antiquities
WTTC	World tourism and travel council
CNN	Cable news network
LED	Local economic development
NDP	National development plan
UNDP	United nations development plan
TBL	Triple bottom line theory
COVID-19	Corona Virus Disease Of 2019
IV	Independent variable
DV	Dependent variable
CREATOUR	Creative tourism
WTO	World tourism organization
SPSS	Social package for statistical science
SDG	Sustainable development goals

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ABSTRACT

This study was about the Development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas of Uganda. The objectives of the study were; to assess the current state of tourism in small towns surrounding Lake Mburo National Park, to identify factors hindering the development of tourism in the developing country like Uganda, to propose strategies for promoting tourism and sustainable development in the small towns surrounding Lake Mburo national park. The researcher based on theory of triple bottom line and conceptual considerations to explain more about the dependent variable and the independent variable. Data was collected using descriptive cross sectional survey employing quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, this study design was selected because it assisted in getting the required data for the study easily. The study population was 40 and the target population was 36 from which the data was collected, the researcher later used sample technique of collecting data and this was simple random sampling and it was carried out in four departments of the area. The data was collected using a close ended questionnaire and data was presented using frequency tables and the correlation and regression results were obtained. Collected data was analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively. The data sources were both from primary and secondary which helped the researcher to be equipped with much information. The analysis of data was carried out through the use of computerized software (SPSS) and qualitative statistical techniques were used to describe and summarize data. The presentation of data was done through use of tables which hold results of correlation and regression and bio data. Then the findings were made basing on different objectives which a researcher gave a clear conclusion from the findings. The study recommended enhancing tourism infrastructure and services to drive small town development, emphasizing the need for targeted marketing, improved funding, and strategic stakeholder engagement. In conclusion, effective tourism promotion and infrastructure upgrades can significantly benefit small towns, fostering sustainable growth and community involvement.

CHAPTER ONE

BACKGROUND OF STUDY

1.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the Background of study, Statement of the Problem, Purpose of the study, Research objectives, Research questions, Scope of the Study, Content Scope, Geographical Scope, Time Scope, Significance of the Study and Conceptual Framework.

1.1 Back ground of the study.

The study is about the development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas of Uganda. The study is important because it helps in improving the small towns in scenic areas economically, socially and environmentally well.

Small towns, are defined as those with fewer than 20,000 inhabitants (Majewska et al., 2022), are diverse and face significant challenges, including population decline and economic crises due to competition from larger cities and reduced rural services (Bartosiewicz and Marszał, 2013; Heffner and Halama, 2011; Heffner, 2005). These issues drive many small towns to explore local or regional tourism development as an economic stimulus. Defining small towns can be approached practically, using population size or legal criteria, or scientifically, focusing on their economic, administrative, or cultural importance (Steinführer et al., 2016). Functional definitions emphasize their role in connecting metropolitan and rural areas and balancing settlement systems (Filipović et al.; Hinderink and Titus, 1988). Scenic areas for tourism can be defined as places with significant natural or human features that attract tourists (Leiper, 1990; Pearce, 1991), (Lu, 2022)

Historical sites are common in small towns across Poland, with some recognized as UNESCO World Heritage Sites. This paper explores how these sites contribute to the tourism potential of these towns and highlights regional differences in their ability to develop tourism. It provides a typology of towns based on natural, cultural, and accommodation factors, using data from Statistics Poland (2012-2014) and the National Heritage Board of Poland. The study reveals that having a historical site does not automatically lead to a thriving local tourism sector, suggesting that cultural resources are often underutilized but could be key to local tourism development, especially for towns seeking new growth opportunities. (Kwiatek-Sołtys & Bajgier-Kowalska, 2019)

In Eastern Europe, particularly Poland, small towns are known for their tourism attractiveness due to their history, former function, ethnic structure, and cultural heritage resources. These towns make up 75% of all urban settlements in Poland and are home to 21.6% of the urban population. However, in the era of globalization, many small towns are facing a deep social and economic crisis due to population loss and decline in key urban functions. Traditional urban formation mechanisms are weak, and many small towns are experiencing stagnation due to poor municipal financial situation and high unemployment. This neglect of cultural landscape and historical sites is a serious threat to their continued development.

The role of cultural heritage is often marginalized in research literature on small towns and their development, especially when it does not yield direct financial gains. McMorran (2008) noted that heritage is employed as an element that is both profitable and desired by tourists, not because it is a key witness to history. Murzyn-Kupisz (2012) discussed the role of cultural heritage in local development, while Jamieson (1993) examined the issue of cultural heritage tourism in small Canadian towns. The starting point for Jamieson's analysis was the economic crisis and the need to find new development pathways (Kwiatek-Sołtys & Bajgier-Kowalska, 2019). Matei and Caraba (2010) and Fonseca and Ramos (2012) highlighted the challenges faced by small towns in developing their tourism sector, highlighting the need for infrastructure, investors, qualified workers, and a robust service sector. Steele (2017) emphasized the growing popularity of rural tourism in small towns, leading to the emergence of new types such as slow food, cittaslow, authentic tourism, geotourism, agritourism, and heritage tourism. However, many small towns fear becoming 'Aspenized', which can lead to unaffordable conditions for workers or native residents.

In Poland, many small towns have numerous cultural heritage sites, which can influence their tourism potential. This paper aims to determine the role of these sites in shaping the tourism potential of these

towns, focusing on historical sites protected by Polish law. The analysis aims to show regional differences and the relationship between tourism potential and actual utilization, measured via incoming tourist flow, including foreign tourist flow. (Kwiatek-Sołtys & Bajgier-Kowalska, 2019)

In recent years, China's urban and rural development has significantly improved, leading to accelerated urbanization and improved living quality. People now prioritize spiritual needs and enjoyment over material needs, leading to increased demands for tourism. This has unified the development of small towns and characteristic tourism in many regions, leading to rapid growth in the tourism industry. Small towns of tourist reception are a key to the construction of about 70% of scenic spots. They directly bring tourists a sense of the quality of these spots, positively affecting the development of scenic spots and adjusting industrial structures. This also promotes local employment and economic development, as they directly contribute to the overall development of the region. (He, 2019)

In Africa, particularly in South Africa, since the end of apartheid, South African scholars have increasingly focused on small-town development, primarily addressing local economic development (LED) (Nel 1994, Nel and Hill 1996, Marais 2004, Ndlovu and Rogerson 2004, Nel 2005). Other studies have explored small-town developmental potential, boundary disputes (Ramutsindela 1998, Giraut and Maharaj 2002), and municipal issues (Timm et al. 1998). Recently, research has shifted towards tourism development in small towns (Briedenhann and Wickens 2004, Hoogendoorn and Visser 2004, Donaldson 2007, Ferreira 2007, Halseth and Meiklejohn 2009, Hoogendoorn et al. 2009). It is noted that, similar to international trends, tourism is seen as a key opportunity to leverage underutilized local assets and attract external spending, given the decline of traditional economic activities in many areas (Hoogendoorn & Visser, 2016: 99). (Donaldson et al., 2012) and (Rogerson, 2016). In addition to the above, the promotion of small towns and leveraging their role for local development in surrounding rural areas is considered in certain African countries (most notably Ghana) as a vehicle for successful poverty reduction and the achievement of United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (Owusu, 2015, 2018).

In the east African region particularly at Lamu (Kenya) and at Zanzibar (Tanzania), the growth of tourism in East African coastal towns like Lamu and Zanzibar is controversial due to the juxtaposition of rich visitors and poor locals, which can lead to exploitation, cultural attrition, and violence. The small towns offer pedestrian-friendly environments and buildings of interest to many cultural tourists. Extra-urban beach-related hotel complexes offer alternative accommodation, but the growth of tourism is a controversial phenomenon. Tanzania, especially Zanzibar, has been reluctant to encourage the growth of tourism until

recently, but the potential value of a well-organized tourist industry to the country's weak economy has led to more open policies in this context. (Okech, 2007). In contrast, Kenya's tourist industry, in the context of that country's more capitalist economy, continues generally to flourish and to provide at least some worthwhile economic advantages for the coastal small towns. Lamu stands, however, on the fringes of this industry, geographically and structurally; that is part of its character and its attraction, (Okech, 2007)

Tourism is a complex phenomenon requiring a multidisciplinary approach for full understanding (Candela & Figini, 2012). It significantly impacts people's lives, with many involved directly or indirectly (Hannam & Paris, 2014; Kwiatek-Sołtys & Bajgier-Kowalska, 2019). In 2022, tourism contributed about US\$5.81 trillion to global GDP, or 6.1%, making it a top export industry. Pre-pandemic in 2019, tourism created 10.3% of global jobs and generated US\$1.8 trillion from international visitors. However, COVID-19 drastically reduced these figures, with international arrivals dropping to 917 million in 2022 (WTTC, 2022; MTWA Tourism Statistical Abstract 2024). Tourism development involves creating strategies to boost tourism in specific destinations (Schegg & Stangl, 2017). While tourism thrives in countries like Switzerland, Indonesia, and Hawaii, East Africa, particularly Kenya, leads in development. Uganda's tourism focuses on wildlife reserves such as Bwindi and Queen Elizabeth National Parks (Shakur & Alabi, 2018; LMNP, n.d.). The EAC region's tourism sector contributes roughly 17% to export earnings, 10% to GDP, and generates about 7% of regional employment.(eac).

In 2019, tourism contributed the following percentages to GDP/exports and employment earnings in East African Community (EAC) Partner States: Burundi 5.1%, Kenya 9.7%, Rwanda 10.0%, Tanzania 10.3%, and Uganda 5.6%, averaging 8.1% (Muoki, 2021; African Nature Based Tourism Platform, 2022). The EAC Vision 2050 aims to enhance tourism through competitive pricing, cost-effective strategies, and high returns on investment, including an East African Visa, standardized hotel classifications, and joint marketing efforts. The EAC's collective approach, as outlined in Article 115 of the EAC Treaty, focuses on promoting multi-destination tourism to boost regional and international tourism. This aligns with regional and international development goals, including Agenda 2063's emphasis on cultural heritage and NEPAD's Tourism Action Plan, as well as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which highlight tourism's role in job creation, poverty reduction, and climate change mitigation.(East African Community, 2016)

Uganda, a landlocked country bordered by Kenya, Sudan, Tanzania, Rwanda, and the Democratic Republic of Congo (King et al., 2023), relies heavily on tourism as an economic driver. In the 2018–2019 financial year, tourism contributed 5.6 trillion Ugandan shillings (US\$1.60 billion or €1.3 billion) to Uganda's GDP

from 1.6 million tourists (World Bank 2019). In 2019, tourism directly impacted 3.1% of GDP. However, the sector saw a 55% decline from March to June 2020, with a reduced contribution of 2.5% to GDP in 2020 (World Travel and Tourism Council, 2021). The Directorate of Citizenship and Immigration controls legal border movements through various entry/exit points, with information gathered from arrival and departure cards (Statistics et al., 2021).

In the 1960s, Uganda's tourism industry was thriving, significantly contributing to the country's exports, with international arrivals reaching 85,000 by 1997 and generating US\$20 million annually (Byamugisha, 1993). However, under Idi Amin's rule, tourism declined due to political instability, press censorship, and a focus on military spending. Visitor numbers plummeted from 5,000 in 1977 to just 1,000 in 1978 and tourism's foreign exchange earnings dropped (Tread away, 1974). Today, tourism is rapidly growing, with about 1.5 million visitors annually, contributing 7.7% to GDP (Uganda Investment Authority; Richter et al., 2019.). Uganda was named a top travel destination by CNN in 2023 and is expanding its tourism beyond traditional safaris. Projections suggest 1.4 million tourist arrivals in 2023 (econometric models, 2023). Uganda Vision 2040 highlights tourism as crucial for socio-economic transformation, job creation, and poverty reduction, aiming to develop both primary and secondary industries through tourism's wide multiplier effects (NDP, 2013).

Lake Mburo National Park, initially a Controlled Hunting Area in 1933 and upgraded to a Game Reserve in 1963, achieved National Park status in 1983, partly as a strategy to weaken the Banyankole who opposed the Obote government. This led to tensions, as the displaced pastoralists received no compensation. By 1985, after the Obote regime fell, these residents reoccupied the park, resulting in severe damage to infrastructure and wildlife. The park, covering 370 km² with five lakes, offers year-round tourism opportunities, including game drives, boat trips, and horseback riding, with accommodations like Mihingo Lodge and Mantana Tented Camp (UGfacts.net, 2019; English & Ahebwa, 2019). Despite its attractions, nearby small towns such as Sanga face challenges in capitalizing on tourism due to limited infrastructure and access to information, resulting in stagnant local economies. Consequently, while the park draws tourists, its economic benefits are skewed towards larger hubs, leaving small towns in need of strategies to bridge this gap and ensure sustainable development (LMNP, n.d.).

To develop tourism in small scenic towns, this study will use the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) theory (Elkington, 1994), aligned with sustainable development principles from the late 1980s (WCED, 1987). The TBL approach, which considers environmental, social, and economic impacts, is relevant due to

tourism's interplay with its natural and social settings (Faux & Dwyer, 2009). Benefits of TBL in tourism include cost savings, better market positioning, improved stakeholder relationships, and enhanced destination competitiveness (Tyrrell et al., 2012). Applying TBL in scenic small towns promotes tourism development while emphasizing sustainability through environmental conservation, socio-cultural practices, and economic growth.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite tourism efforts in Kiruhura district, small towns remain impoverished and lack control over tourism management. Local communities, often with low literacy, are excluded from decision-making by tourism agencies (Koc et al., 2017). Additionally, poor communities struggle to attract resources for necessary tourism infrastructure, and higher-status community members may not act in the broader community's best interest. Communities around Lake Mburo National Park also face challenges due to limited information, resources, and power, and often lack ownership of land and natural resources, which are controlled by outsiders (Goodwin, 2008). This research examines the role of small towns in tourism development in Uganda, focusing on Lake Mburo National Park, Kiruhura district.

1.3 Purpose of the study

To develop tourism in small towns of scenic areas of Uganda with Lake Mburo National Park, Kiruhura as the case study.

1.4 Research objectives

- i. To assess the current state of tourism in small towns surrounding Lake Mburo National Park.
- ii. To identify factors hindering the development of tourism in the developing country like Uganda.
- iii. To propose strategies for promoting tourism and sustainable development in the small towns surrounding lake Mburo national park.

1.5 Research questions

- i. How has the COVID-19 pandemic impacted tourism in the Lake Mburo National Park area and what are the lessons learned for future resilience and recovery?
- ii. What are the perceptions and attitudes of local residents towards the tourism industry, and how do these factors contribute to or hinder the sustainable development of tourism in the region?
- iii. What are the challenges and opportunities faced by small businesses in the tourism sector within the scenic areas around Lake Mburo National Park?
- iv. What role do local community engagement and participation play in the sustainable development of tourism in small towns around scenic areas like Lake Mburo National Park?

1.6 Scope of the Study

- i. The scope of the study covers three dimensions and these are; content, geographical and time and these were discussed in detail below;

1.6.1 Content Scope

- ii. The study will focus on the development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas of Uganda, with Lake Mburo national park as the case study.

1.6.2 Geographical Scope

- iii. The study is focused majorly on the western part of Uganda, Ankole region (Ankole- Masaka cattle corridor), focusing on the small towns near the scenic area, known as Lake Mburo national park.

1.6.3 Time Scope

- iv. The time scope of this research focuses on the period of 2021 to the period of 2024 and this focused on finding out the development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas of Uganda.

1.7 Significance of the Study

- i. The research is to be used for further research in line with the study topic by acting as a reference to other people who may conduct research in the same topic of study.
- ii. The study will also be relevant to the area of the case study that is Lake Mburo national park especially to the management in proper coordination with the community.
- iii. The outcome of the study is thus expected to contribute to the knowledge of understanding of who is involved in the development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas, their roles, and the benefits they receive from their involvement and the subsequent contribution to regional development in Kiruhura district. This will be instrumental in identifying the scope for new recommendations for both spatial and non-spatial improvements of small towns.
- iv. The research was a requirement by the University for the Award of bachelor's degree in tourism and travel management of Busitema University.

Figure 1: Conceptual frame work showing the relationship between small towns in scenic areas and tourism development

1.8 Conceptual framework

Mugenda (2008) defines conceptual framework as a concise description of the phenomenon under study accompanied by a graphical or visual depiction of the major variables of the study. According to Young (2009), conceptual framework is a diagrammatical representation that shows the relationship between

dependent variable and independent variables. In the study, the conceptual framework will look at the relationship between small towns in scenic areas and tourism development.

The conceptual framework showing the relationship between tourism development and small towns in scenic areas;

**TOURISM DEVELOPMENT (IV)
(DV)**

SMALL TOWNS IN SCENIC AREAS

Adopted and modified from, Nolitha KONTSIWE, 2019

Nolitha Kontsiwe's (2019) conceptual framework provides a unique perspective on tourism development and its impact on small towns in scenic areas. It focuses on the unique economic and social dynamics shaped by tourism, allowing for a targeted analysis of aspects such as infrastructure development, economic growth, community well-being, and environmental sustainability. This approach leads to tailored policy recommendations and strategic interventions to maximize the positive impacts of tourism while mitigating potential negative effects. This approach contributes to the sustainable development of tourism destinations

and enhances the resilience and inclusivity of local communities, making Kontsiwe's framework a valuable choice for stakeholders involved in regional development and tourism planning.

1.8.1 Explanation of the Conceptual Framework

The framework examines the factors influencing small towns in scenic areas, including tourism assessment, infrastructure, demographics, and economic impacts. It compares these with tourism barriers like safety, security, regulatory issues, and environmental issues. It also considers factors related to tourism promotion, such as environmental sustainability and community involvement. The dependent variable is outcomes like improved infrastructure, increased tourism revenue, private enterprise profitability, and sustainable practices. The framework aims to understand the interplay between these elements, providing insights for sustainable growth and development in picturesque towns. (*Nolitha KONTSIWE, 2019*)

1.9 Definitions of terms used in the study

1.9.1 Tourism Development: According to Rivera, Croes, and Lee (2016), tourism development is a multidimensional structure involving economic, social, environmental and cultural conditions.

1.9.2 Small Towns: Small towns can be defined as towns of fewer than 20,000 inhabitants (Kwiątek-Sołtys & Bajgier-Kowalska, 2019)T constitute a very diverse set of settlements (Bartosiewicz and Marszał, 2013; Heffner and Halama, 2011).

1.9.3 Scenic Areas: Scenic areas are locations, typically natural, that are visually appealing or picturesque. These areas often boast stunning landscapes, such as mountains, valleys, rivers, forests, coastlines, or other natural features. Scenic areas are frequently visited by tourists, photographers, and nature enthusiasts seeking to appreciate their beauty and capture memorable moments. (UNESCO, 2017) and (Tessema et al., 2021).

CHAPTER TWO:

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This study was set out to assess the development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas of Uganda taking the case study of Lake Mburo national park, Kiruhura district. This chapter covered the related literature to the topic of the study. The literature was in line with the study objectives.

2.1 Theoretical review

The researcher used Triple bottom line theory to assess the development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas and below is the detail discussion and review of the theory.

2.1.1 Triple bottom line theory

The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) concept aligns with the sustainable development ideas from the late 1980s (WCED, 1987). Introduced by Elkington (1994), TBL expands traditional economic profitability by including social and environmental dimensions. It aims to foster sustainable development and is used for comprehensive performance measurement and reporting (Elkington, 1997; Faux, 2005). The TBL framework supports decision-making and reporting across various industries and has been endorsed by the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (Vandenberg, 2002). In tourism, TBL can drive conservation, enhance community well-being, and benefit multiple stakeholders, making it a valuable tool for promoting sustainable practices in small scenic towns (Buckley, 2003; Faux & Dwyer, 2009). This approach helps in achieving efficiencies, improved market positioning, and strategic benefits (Tyrrell et al., 2012).

2.1.2 Assessing the current state of tourism in small towns surrounding scenic areas

Local participation in tourism development is often seen as a positive driver for change in small towns near natural attractions, potentially boosting national development. However, Nsizwazikhona and Nduduzo (2017) argue that this view is overly simplistic. While promoting local participation seems straightforward, its practical implementation is complex. Assumptions that residents are always willing and able to participate equally are debated (Hanafiah et al., 2013). Though local involvement is considered crucial for sustainable tourism (Lekaota, 2015), in reality, residents frequently have limited roles in decision-making and management (Stone & Stone, 2011). Ideally, communities would control tourism development, but often they lack the experience, resources, and interest necessary for successful ventures (Rogersson & Letsie, 2013).and(Thetsane, 2019).

In the context of ‘over-tourism’ in most of small towns and coastal resort communities, CREATOUR (creative tourism) aims to develop attractive offers in ‘other’, less visited areas, focusing on rural areas and small towns and cities. CREATOUR promotes small-scale, interactive creative tourism activities, building from local cultural traditions, skills, knowledge, and emerging artistic practices. The initiatives are supported by a network offering not only visibility through critical mass, but also aimed to support research, co-learning, and capacity building. The project aims to contribute to the sustainable development of local communities across the country, and encourages (and will monitor) the wider community impacts of the creative tourism pilots (Duxbury et al., 2019). This is also another current state of tourism in small towns surrounding scenic areas.

Carrying capacity is a key issue for tourism in small scenic towns, balancing tourist numbers with environmental and developmental goals to ensure long-term economic viability. This concept, crucial for sustainable tourism, is applied pragmatically and theoretically, especially in protected areas and popular attractions. It addresses the balance between tourism growth and the preservation of local lifestyles and the destination's overall potential. It also involves considering economic, social, and environmental dimensions to maintain sustainability. (Sadrija & Desku, 2022) The World Tourism Organization (WTO, 2019) has defined the Tourism carrying Capacity as the maximum number of persons who can visit a site within a given period.

The literature suggests a significant research gap in the practical implementation and inclusivity of tourism development initiatives, especially in small towns near natural attractions. While theoretical frameworks emphasize local participation for sustainable tourism, there is a lack of empirical studies examining barriers that prevent residents from effectively participating in decision-making processes and managing tourist activities. Initiatives like CREATOUR can address these challenges and foster community involvement, enhancing inclusivity and sustainability in small towns and rural settings.

2.1.3 Identifying factors hindering the development of tourism in the developing countries like Uganda.

There are various factors hindering the development of tourism in the developing countries country and these are cited from the articles of (Selemon et al., 2019) and (Biswas, 2020);

Parvaneh (2013) described that “infrastructure barrier is one of the major barrier in tourism development including lack of or poor transport vehicles for passengers, intercity roads, shopping centres, power, water and telecommunications, sanitation and hygiene networks in tourism areas”. Taleghani et al. (2014)

assessed a significant relationship between weaknesses of infrastructural facilities and underdevelopment of tourism industry. Tourism infrastructure includes roads, railways, airports, health care systems, services and public services. Additionally, it includes some ancillary and complementary facilities, equipment, systems, process and resources that are necessary for the functioning of any tourist destination (Jovanović and Ilić, 2016).

According to (Kantawateera et al., 2015), lack of or poor public transportation system and traffic jam are major problem in many destinations of the developing countries. Although some destinations can be reached by air, flight options are not enough for meeting all demands of tourists and other passengers. Moreover, the rail transportation is not up to the standard while bus services are not reliable. Even, public transportation system that link to the tourist destination is mostly seen difficult to access. For these reasons, Kantawateera et al. (2015) claimed that transportation problem is one of the main causes that hinder tourism development.

According to Ghaderi, Saboori, and Khoshkam (2017), safety and security are critical for tourism development, as tourists are highly sensitive to these factors. Successful tourism destinations must offer a secure environment, as many developing countries face safety issues that deter visitors (Kim, 2003). Security concerns, such as terrorism, crime, and political instability, hinder tourism development and lead to negative perceptions (Sharifinia, 2014). Incidents or unrest can undermine tourists' confidence and disrupt their experience, impacting their view of the destination (Sandeep & Vinod, 2014).

Inadequate hospitality services, including accommodation, food, entertainment, and shopping, are significant barriers to tourism development. Tourists expect high-quality lodging and services, which many developing countries struggle to provide due to limited accommodation options and a lack of nearby restaurants (Gee, Makens, & Choy, 1984). Countries like Uganda often have few luxury hotels and inadequate dining facilities, which do not meet tourist expectations. Unlike advanced countries that effectively attract tourists with diverse dining options, developing nations lag behind due to the unavailability of restaurants and fast food options near tourist lodgings (Ardabili & Rasouli, 2011).

Many developing countries face inadequate water supply and poor sanitation, which pose significant threats to tourism development (Frone & Frone, 2013). Issues such as inadequate water treatment, limited access to centralized water, and inefficient sewerage systems jeopardize both tourist and environmental safety. Insufficient wastewater treatment directly harms tourist perceptions and negatively impacts the tourism

industry. The lack of trained staff further reduces the effectiveness of water treatment, leading to sanitation problems for tourists.

According to Arabzadeh, Arabzadeh, Bavarsad, and Arabzadeh (2015), there is a shortage of promotional campaigns and marketing representatives particularly in many developing countries to promote and market their tourist destinations internationally. Gnanapala (2015) mentioned that numerous promotional and marketing activities can attract more tourists and improve their perception towards tourist destination. Basically, two marketing weaknesses are considered as major deterrent in tourism development. These include the absence of information about destinations in tour operators' catalogues as well as lack of international promotional campaigns and marketing representatives (Samardali-kakai, 2013).

Taleghani et al. (2014) highlight a significant barrier to tourism development: the lack of a culture of accepting tourists. Cultural differences between tourists and hosts can lead to negative perceptions, with hosts often unaware of tourists' needs and tourists lacking understanding of the local culture (Parvaneh, 2013; Arabzadeh et al., 2015). Language barriers also pose challenges, as many service providers speak only English, making it difficult for non-English speakers to communicate and access information (Eun et al., n.d.). Additionally, the shortage of multilingual tour guides exacerbates these issues, affecting tourists' overall experience.

Based on the literature reviewed from various sources (Selemon et al., 2019; Biswas, 2020; Parvaneh, 2013; Taleghani et al., 2014; Kantawateera et al., 2015; Ghaderi et al., 2017; Gee et al., 1984; Frone and Frone, 2013; Arabzadeh et al., 2015), significant barriers to tourism development in developing countries like Uganda have been identified, including inadequate infrastructure, poor transportation systems, safety concerns, insufficient hospitality services, sanitation issues, and inadequate marketing efforts. However, there remains a gap in understanding the nuanced interplay and relative importance of these barriers across different regions within developing countries, which could provide insights into tailored strategies for sustainable tourism development.

2.1.4 Proposing strategies for promoting tourism and sustainable development in the small towns surrounding scenic areas.

Remember, the concept of sustainable tourism development is generally recognized in leading countries of the world and in a number of international organizations, including the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), the International Federation of Tour Operators (IFTO) and others.(Shichiyakh, 2019)

Below are the strategies for promoting tourism and sustainable development in small towns surrounding scenic areas;

Awareness of local societies; According to (Kaila, 2002), The dispersion of the concept of sustainable tourism development does not leave societies unaffected, especially if these live in environmentally sensitive areas. In such areas the ideological aspect of sustainable development influences substantially the ways of thinking, the beliefs as well as all sorts of practices and activities. Of course this change takes place if citizens adopt the concept and realize that only through a sustainable tourism development strategy, welfare and prosperity from tourism could last in the long run.

The advertising of tourist products nationally and internationally is also another significant strategy of promoting tourism and sustainable development in rural areas as well as small towns. According to (Ilollari, 2023), the country's unique cultural and natural attractions, combined with its rich history and warm hospitality, make it an attractive destination for tourists from around the world. Effective advertising campaigns have helped to raise the country's profile and increase tourist numbers, contributing to economic growth, job creation, profits and sustainable practices.

Sustaining the growth of the tourism industry requires a coordinated effort from all stakeholders. The government, private sector, and local communities must work together to ensure the industry develops sustainably, minimizing its impact on the environment and cultural heritage. This will require careful planning and the adoption of best practices in sustainable tourism development, including the promotion of eco-tourism, cultural tourism, and adventure tourism(Scheyvens et al., 2016).

To maintain sustainable growth and success, it is important to continue investing in the industry and to implement sustainable development practices and strategic planning. Furthermore, the tourism industry has the potential to become a key sector for the country's economic growth. With the development of new destinations, improvement of infrastructure, and effective marketing strategies, Uganda's tourism industry can attract more visitors and generate greater economic benefits(Ilollari, 2023). By focusing on sustainable development practices, such as promoting eco-tourism and responsible tourism, the industry can also contribute to the preservation of natural and cultural resources(Ridho & Alisa, 2020).

Additionally, providing training and education for local communities can help to promote cultural heritage and enhance the visitor experience. Overall, the government and the tourism industry must work together to create a sustainable future for tourism in the country. By prioritizing sustainable development practices,

investing in infrastructure, and effectively promoting Uganda as a destination, the industry can continue to play a vital role in the country's economic growth and sustainable development (Ilollari, 2023).

The literature on promoting tourism and sustainable development in small towns near scenic areas highlights key strategies like awareness campaigns, advertising, stakeholder collaboration, and sustainable practices. However, there is a research gap in understanding the practical implementation and measurable outcomes of these strategies. Specifically, there is a need for empirical evidence on their impact on the long-term sustainability and economic growth of these towns. Additionally, more research is needed on the effectiveness of educational programs for preserving cultural heritage and enhancing visitor experiences. Addressing these gaps could refine existing strategies and develop new, context-specific approaches for sustainable tourism.

2.2 summary of the literature reviewed

The literature review on the development of tourism in small towns surrounding Lake Mburo National Park in Uganda reveals a nascent industry with untapped potential but limited infrastructure and promotional activities. Factors hindering tourism development include poor infrastructure, inadequate funding, lack of skilled personnel, and limited marketing efforts. The review incorporates the Triple Bottom Line Theory, emphasizing the need for a balanced approach considering economic, social, and environmental impacts for sustainable tourism development. Strategies for promoting tourism include enhancing infrastructure, investing in local stakeholder training, and creating comprehensive marketing campaigns. However, gaps in research include a lack of detailed case studies and longitudinal data on socio-economic impacts.

CHAPTER THREE:

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction:

This chapter explained the methodology that was used to conduct the research, procedures of data collection, research design, the study area and the population, sampling procedures, sampling size and composition, data collection methods, data quality control, and ethical consideration.

3.1 Research Design

The study involved the use of cross sectional research design. A cross section research design entailed the collection of data to make inferences about the population of interest at one point in time (Abuja 2009). The design was used for the study because it provides quick, efficient and accurate means of accessing information about the population being studied. As cited by (Mohammed et al., 2021), according to Kotari (2003), research design is the arrangement of conditions for collection, analysis and presentation of data in sequential frameworks to reach the intended end.

3.2 Study Population

As cited by (Rahi, 2017), according to (Schindler & Cooper, 2014), defined population as the element which we wish to make inference on, thus it is the total collection of elements about which one will intend to make inference. The study targeted a population of 40 respondents both working in the national park and the small towns surrounding the national park.

3.3 Sample Size

The study used a sample 36 from the target respondent of 40 and this includes people working in the national park as well in the small towns surrounding the national park in the different departments. The Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table is used for determining sample size from the population.

Table 1: shows a sampling frame

Categories of respondent	Proposed sample	Actual sample	Sampling method
Onsite guides	10	9	Random sampling
The local community leaders in small towns	15	13	Random sampling
Conservation department	7	7	Purposive sampling
Tourists/visitors	8	7	Purposive sampling
Total	40	36	

Source: Krejcie & Morgan, (1970)

3.4 Sample techniques

The study employed purposive and simple random sampling methods to select respondents. Simple random sampling was employed in departments with a larger population to prevent bias and ensure equal selection, while purposive sampling was employed in departments with a smaller population to ensure all respondents were included in data collection.

3.5 Sources of data

The source of data mainly entailed primary and secondary data sources.

3.5.1 Primary source

The primary data was important for all areas of research because it gives accurate information about the result of an experiment or observation. The researcher administered questionnaires to the selected respondents both in the national park and in the small towns surrounding the national park in order to get their opinions and this was to help the researcher in the collection of information for the specific purpose of the study.

3.5.2 Secondary source

Secondary data refer to handling, collecting and possibly processing data by people other than the researcher in question. For the purposes of a historical research project, secondary sources are generally scholarly books and pamphlets, research proposals and reports, online journals and other publications. This source will be used to collect data from already written literature for example e books, journals, published articles and periodicals. Documentary resources will be classified in order to facilitate the data collection and the textual analysis.

3.6 Data collection methods and instruments

Data collection is a methodical process of gathering and analyzing specific information to offer solutions to relevant questions and evaluate the results. The study incorporates self-completion data collection method

where all the respondents identified will be given a questionnaire to fill in the question that will be presented by the researcher.

The instrument is structured with closed ended questionnaire which are measured on the 5point scale, where 5(Strongly agree), 4(agree), 3(Not sure), 2(dis agree) and 1(strongly dis agree). This will be used because they are time saving and easy for the respondent to answer in that respondent is a given chance to tick the appropriate answer of his or her choice hence improving on the consistence of the response (Polit and Beck, 2012). Follow up will be made to ensure that there is an adequate completion rate by respondent within the stipulated time.

3.7 Data collection procedure

The researcher obtained an introductory letter from the faculty of management sciences at Busitema University and seeks permission from the national park management to use the place for data collection. The researcher approached respondents and distributed questionnaires with question items and statements. The responses were collected, analyzed, and a conclusion drawn at the end of the study. The study aimed to gather valuable insights from the respondents.

3.8 Reliability and validity

3.8.1 Validity of results

The researcher will ensure validity of the tools to be used in data collection first by carrying out pretest where 10 questions will be distributed to 5 employees of the national park and another 5 for community members with in the small towns near the national park as well in order to ensure the reliability of the survey instruments which will be utilized and the effectiveness of the research design in general. The set questions will first be sent to the academic supervisor to assess whether they match with the study objectives and corrections will be made basing on the opinion of the academic supervisor.

3.8.2Reliabilty of the results

A pilot study was carried out in the five different departments where the respondents belonged before sending the questionnaire to them.

Table 2: Reliability and validity of results

Variables	No.of items	Cronbach's alpha	CVI
Tourism current status assessment	7	.777	.773
Tourism barriers	7	.873	.750
Tourism promotion	7	.788	.792
Small towns in scenic areas.	10	.787	.757

Source: Primary data, (2024)

3.9 Data analysis plan

Data analysis is the process of systematically applying statistical and or logical techniques to describe, illustrate, condense, recap, and evaluate data. The data collected will be coded, keyed into SPSS (a computerized software data base), organized and cleaned for any errors that will occur during data collection. The data will then be analyzed using statistics with aid of the SPSS version 20.

3.10 Ethical consideration

The researcher will seek for official permission to gather the data from the respondents in the national park and the small town near the national park by providing the introductory letter from the university for the purpose of identification. Which will promote ethics in this study, the researcher will ensure confidentiality by not including names of respondents who will help in data collection for this study.

The researcher will also ensure coordination and corporation among many different people who will be involved in the study especially the respondents through phone calls and physically travelling to them.

CHAPTER 4

DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION, AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the results of data analysis and interpretation of the researcher's findings. For this study, data analysis and interpretation of finding is guided by the following study objectives;

- i. To assess the current state of tourism in small towns surrounding Lake Mburo National Park.
- ii. To identify factors hindering the development of tourism in the developing country like Uganda.
- iii. To propose strategies for promoting tourism and sustainable development in the small towns surrounding lake Mburo national park.

Table 3: Response Rate

The researcher gave out 36 questionnaires, and all questionnaires were turned, representing a response rate of 100%; the findings are shown in the table below;

Target respondents	No. of questionnaires returned	Response rate
36	36	100%

4.1 Demographic information

The demographic information presented on the gender, age, level of education, position in the national park or small towns and period of existence of the national park

4.2 Gender of the respondents

The researcher requested the respondents to provide their gender details and their responses were analyzed as shown in the table 4 below;

Table 4 showing responses by gender;

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	male	16	44.4	44.4
	female	20	55.6	100.0
	Total	36	100.0	100.0

Source: primary data, (2024)

Table 4 shows that 16 (44.4%) were male, and 20 (55.6%) were female. The majority of the respondents were female as compared to male, and this implies that there was gender bias in small towns near Lake Mburo national park. This may be giving the small towns leaders in implementing its practices since such people react to passionate changes of the small towns and female work best in terms of offering services, running small businesses in the small towns compared to male.

4.2.2 Age of the respondents

The respondents were further asked to indicate their age. Table 4.2.2 shows the results of the study;

Table 5 respondents categorized by age bracket

Age range	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-25	4	11.1	11.1	11.1
26-35	4	11.1	11.1	22.2
Valid 36-45	14	38.9	38.9	61.1
46-55	7	19.4	19.4	80.6
55 and above	7	19.4	19.4	100.0
Total	36	100.0	100.0	

Source: primary data, (2024)

Table 5 above, the findings indicated that 4(11.1%) of the respondents were aged between 18-25 years, 4(11.1%) of the respondents were aged between 26-35 years of age, 14(38.9%) of the respondents were aged between, 36-45 years, 7(19.4%) of the respondents were aged between 46-55 years and also the other 7(19.4%) were aged 55 and above. This implies that most of the people living in small towns of the scenic area of lake Mburo national park, are young, energetic, committed, and hard working towards the development of tourism since they engage themselves in tourism related activities such selling street foods, artifacts among others.

4.2.3 Education back ground

Table 6: academic level of education attained

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	certificate	6	16.7	16.7	16.7
	diploma	12	33.3	33.3	50.0
	bachelors	12	33.3	33.3	83.3
	post graduate	6	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	36	100.0	100.0	

Source: primary data, (2024)

The academic level of the respondents was based on the highest level of education, and the findings were obtained as summarized in the table above; results indicated that, 16.7% had attained a certificate, 33.3% of the respondents had attained a diploma, and also another 33.33% of the respondents had attained a bachelor's degree and 16.7% of the respondents had a post graduate. This therefore shows that most of them had a diploma and bachelors and they are knowledgeable to the level that they can make clear conclusions, mobilization, policy formulation and sensitization in small towns as far the development of tourism is concerned.

Table 7: Position in the national park or small towns;

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	tourists and visitors	6	16.7	16.7	16.7
	conservation department	6	16.7	16.7	33.3
	local businesses	10	27.8	27.8	61.1
	tour guides	8	22.2	22.2	83.3
	local community leaders in small towns	6	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	36	100.0	100.0	

Source: primary data, (2024)

From table 7, the findings indicated that 16.7% of the respondents were tourists and visitors, also another 16.7% were in the conservation department, 27.8% of the respondents were engaged in the local businesses, 22.2% of the respondents were tour guides, and 16.7% of the respondents were local community leaders in small towns. Which means that local businesses have done a lot as far tourism development is concerned in local communities.

Table 8 Organizational (national park) period of existence

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Less than 20 years	1	2.8	2.8	2.8
Valid	20-30 years	9	25.0	25.0	27.8
	30 years and above	26	72.2	72.2	100.0
	Total	36	100.0	100.0	

Source: primary data, (2024)

From table 8, the findings indicated that, 2.8% of the respondents were saying that the park has been in existence for less than 20 years, 25.0% of the respondents were saying that the park has been in existence for the period of between 20 and 30 years and 72.2% of the respondents were saying that the park has been in existence for a period of above 30 years and this was true because even basing on the secondary information I used while doing the background, was showing that lake Mburo national park has been in existence since 1933.

Table 9 Descriptive findings on tourism current status assessment on small towns of scenic areas

Statements	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Tourism in small towns surrounding Lake Mbuero is adequately promoted.	1.00	5.00	3.0833	1.18019
The infrastructure in small towns surrounding Lake Mbuero supports tourism activities effectively.	1.00	5.00	2.9444	1.32976
Accommodation options in small towns surrounding Lake Mbuero meet the needs of tourists.	1.00	5.00	3.0833	1.18019
Small towns surrounding Lake Mbuero offer a variety of tourist attractions and activities.	1.00	5.00	3.0833	1.29560
Safety and security measures in small towns surrounding Lake Mbuero are adequate for tourists.	1.00	5.00	2.9444	1.32976
Local communities in small towns surrounding Lake Mbuero actively participate in tourism development.	2.00	5.00	2.8611	1.29069
Local businesses in small towns surrounding Lake Mbuero actively engage with tourists.	1.00	5.00	2.9444	1.32976
Valid N (listwise)	N=36			

Source: primary data, (2024)

Descriptive statistics for tourism in small towns around Lake Mbuero reveal mixed perceptions among respondents. Tourism promotion scores a moderate 3.08, indicating generally positive but varied views (Min = 1.00, Max = 5.00, Std. Deviation = 1.18). Infrastructure and safety measures both score 2.94, reflecting concerns about their effectiveness (Std. Deviation = 1.33). Accommodation and attractions are rated at 3.08, suggesting satisfactory but improvable conditions (Std. Deviation = 1.18 and 1.30, respectively). Local community participation and business engagement are rated at 2.86 and 2.94,

respectively, showing moderate involvement with room for improvement. These results highlight the need for better tourism infrastructure, safety, community participation, and business engagement to enhance the overall tourism experience in these towns.

Table 10: Descriptive findings on tourism barriers on small towns of scenic areas

Statements	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Insufficient funding allocated to tourism development projects in Uganda	1.00	5.00	2.6944	1.30536
Lack of adequate infrastructure (roads, airports, etc.) for tourism in Uganda.	1.00	5.00	2.7222	1.38587
Limited marketing and promotion efforts for Ugandan tourist destinations.	1.00	5.00	2.7222	1.38587
Inadequate training and education programs for tourism professionals in Uganda.	2.00	5.00	2.6944	1.30536
Lack of safety and security measures for tourists in Uganda.	1.00	5.00	2.8056	1.32707
Limited access to financing and investment opportunities for tourism entrepreneurs in Uganda.	1.00	5.00	2.5833	1.33898
Cultural misunderstandings and conflicts affecting tourism experiences in Uganda.	1.00	5.00	2.9167	1.05221
Valid N (listwise)	N=36			

Source: primary data, (2024)

Table 10 identifies several challenges in Uganda's tourism sector. Key issues include insufficient funding (Mean = 2.6944), inadequate infrastructure (Mean = 2.7222), and limited marketing efforts (Mean = 2.7222). Additionally, there are concerns about inadequate training for tourism professionals (Mean = 2.6944) and safety and security measures (Mean = 2.8056). The sector also faces problems with access to financing (Mean = 2.5833) and cultural misunderstandings (Mean = 2.9167). These findings highlight critical areas needing improvement to enhance tourism development in Uganda.

Table 11: Descriptive findings on tourism promotion strategies on small towns of scenic areas

Statements	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Implementing community-based tourism initiatives to involve local residents in tourism development.	1.00	5.00	2.7778	1.26742
Investing in infrastructure improvement projects (roads, signage, and facilities) in small towns surrounding Lake Mburu National Park.	1.00	5.00	3.0278	1.18288
Establishing eco-friendly accommodation options in the small towns surrounding Lake Mburu National Park.	1.00	5.00	2.8889	1.32617
Collaborating with local businesses to offer authentic and unique tourist experiences.	1.00	5.00	2.9167	1.20416
Enhancing safety and security measures for tourists in the small towns surrounding Lake Mburu National Park	1.00	5.00	2.9167	1.20416
Encouraging responsible tourism practices through education and awareness campaigns.	1.00	5.00	2.8889	1.32617
Implementing marketing and promotional campaigns to attract more visitors to the small towns surrounding Lake Mburu National Park.	1.00	5.00	2.9444	1.32976
Valid N (listwise)	N=36			

Source: primary data, (2024)

The descriptive statistics of table 11 reveal mixed perceptions regarding tourism initiatives in small towns around Lake Mbuo National Park. While there is moderate support for infrastructure investment (Mean = 3.0278) and community-based tourism initiatives (Mean = 2.7778), opinions vary. Establishing eco-friendly accommodations (Mean = 2.8889) and collaborating with local businesses for unique experiences (Mean = 2.9167) also show moderate levels of agreement. Safety and security enhancements (Mean = 2.9167) and promoting responsible tourism practices (Mean = 2.8889) are similarly viewed. Overall, these findings highlight the importance of strategic investments in infrastructure and community engagement, alongside efforts to enhance safety and sustainability, to foster tourism growth in the area effectively.

4.6 Findings from the Objectives

Correlation analysis was used to determine the extent and direction on the effect between independence and dependence variable. We relied on spearman’s rho correlation analysis (r).

This statistical function was there, used to resolve study objectives. The results of this test are summarized in the table below;

Table 12: Correlation Result

VARIABLES		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Tourism current status (1)	1			
	Tourism barriers(2)	.968**	1		
	Tourism promotion strategies (3)	.960**	.973**	1	
Spearman's rho	Small towns of scenic areas (4)	.811**	.902**	.963**	1

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).N=36

Source: primary data, (2024)

4.6.1 Tourism current status assessment and small towns in scenic areas.

From table 4.6 above, the findings indicate a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.811$, $p < 0.01$) between Tourism Current Status Assessment and the Small Towns in Scenic Areas. This suggests that as the assessment of tourism current status increases, there tends to be a corresponding increase in the recognition or development of small towns located in scenic areas, highlighting a significant relationship between these variables within the context of tourism planning and promotion strategies.

4.6.2 Tourism barriers and small towns in scenic areas.

From table 4.6 above, the findings reveal a highly significant positive correlation ($r = 0.902, p < 0.01$) between Tourism Barriers and Small Towns in Scenic Areas. This suggests that as perceived barriers to tourism increase, there is a notable increase in the prominence or development of small towns located in scenic areas. This relationship underscores the potential impact of addressing barriers to tourism on the vitality and recognition of scenic small towns within tourism strategies.

4.6.3 Tourism promotion strategies and small towns in scenic areas.

The findings indicate a very strong positive correlation ($r = 0.963, p < 0.01$) between Tourism Promotion Strategies and Small Towns in Scenic Areas. This suggests that effective promotion strategies in tourism significantly correlate with the development or recognition of small towns situated in scenic areas. This relationship highlights the pivotal role of strategic promotional efforts in enhancing the appeal and visibility of scenic small towns within broader tourism initiatives.

4.7 Regression analysis

The study utilized the simple regression analysis with an aim of establishing the analytical potential of the independent variables, tourism development and the dependent variable, small towns in scenic areas. This analytical frame technique was applied in order to provide clarity on how much variance in the dependent variable (small towns in scenic areas) is explained by independent variables of (tourism current status, tourism barriers, and tourism promotion strategies).

4.7.1 Regression analysis of tourism current status and small towns in scenic areas.

Table 13: Regression analysis of tourism current status on small towns in scenic areas

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.451	1.2357		6.213	.000
	Tourism current status assessment	1.040	.029	.933	439.322	.000
		R=.897^a	R²=.903	Adj R²=.910	F=2332.456	.000^b

Note: N=36, Dependent Variable: Small towns in scenic areas

Source: Primary data, (2024)

The regression model is highly significant ($F = 2332.456$; $p < 0.01$), indicating that the independent variables explain a substantial portion of the variance in the dependent variable. The coefficient for "Tourism current status assessment" is 1.040 with a standard error of .029, showing a strong positive and statistically significant relationship ($t = 439.322$, $p < 0.01$). The R^2 value of .903 indicates that 90.3% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the model, demonstrating a strong fit. Thus, "Tourism current status assessment" is a significant predictor, contributing significantly to explaining the dependent variable's variance.

4.7.2 Regression analysis of tourism barriers and small towns of scenic areas

Table 14: Regression analysis of tourism barriers on small towns of scenic areas

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.565	1.349		4.617	.117
	Tourism	1.886	.052	.740	5.823	.000
	barriers	R=.840^a	R²=740	AdjR²=.732	F=1133.911	.000

Note: N=36, Dependent Variable: Small towns in scenic areas

Source: primary data, (2024)

Regression analysis of tourism barriers reveals a significant positive effect on the development of small towns in scenic areas ($\beta = 1.886$, $p < .001$). With an R^2 of .740, the model explains 74% of the variability in town development. The F-statistic (1133.911) is significant ($p < .001$), validating the model's reliability. The constant term is 7.565, indicating the predicted value when predictors are zero. These results underscore that tourism barriers are a key factor in shaping small towns' development in scenic areas.

4.7.3 Regression analysis of tourism promotion strategies and small towns of scenic areas.

Table 15: Regression analysis of tourism promotion strategies on small towns of scenic areas

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.562	.339		1.660	.108
	Tourism promotion	1.736	.122	.751	6.021	.000
	strategies	R=751^a	R²=.568	Adj R²=.615	F=36.274	.000

Note: N=36, Dependent Variable: Small towns in scenic areas

Source: Primary data, (2023)

Regression analysis reveals that tourism promotion strategies significantly impact the development of small towns in scenic areas ($\beta = 1.736$, $p < .001$). With an R^2 of .568, the model explains 56.8% of the variability in town development. The F-statistic (36.274, $p < .001$) confirms the model's reliability. The constant term (.562) indicates the predicted value when predictors are zero. These results highlight the crucial role of effective tourism promotion strategies in boosting the appeal and development of these towns.

4.7.4 One way Anova of the study objectives.

Table 16: Showing anova of the study objectives

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Tourism current status	20.447	20	1.022	8.994	.000
	1.705	15	.114		
	22.152	35			
Tourism barriers	21.286	20	1.064	1.355	.277
	11.783	15	.786		
	33.070	35			
Tourism promotion strategies	18.421	20	.921	1.702	.149
	8.118	15	.541		
	26.539	35			

Dependent Variable: Small towns in scenic areas. N=36

Source: Primary data, (2024)

The one-way ANOVA results reveal a significant difference in tourism current status among groups ($F(20, 15) = 8.994$, $p < .001$), indicating notable variations that warrant further post-hoc analysis. However, there are no significant differences in tourism barriers ($F(20, 15) = 1.355$, $p = .277$) or tourism promotion strategies ($F(20, 15) = 1.702$, $p = .149$) between groups. These results suggest that while current tourism status varies significantly, perceptions of barriers and promotion strategies are consistent across groups. Further analysis may be needed to explore the implications for tourism development strategies.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

This chapter presented findings, conclusions, recommendations, limitations of the study and areas of further research.

5.1.0 Discussion of the study findings

5.1.1 Tourism current status assessment in small towns of scenic areas

Tourism in small towns near Lake Mbuho National Park is moderately promoted (mean score 3.0833). However, infrastructure and safety measures are viewed as less effective (mean score 2.9444), indicating a need for improvement. Accommodation and tourist attractions are satisfactory but could be better. Community participation and business engagement also show room for improvement. These results underscore the need to enhance infrastructure and local involvement to boost tourism effectiveness, as supported by recent studies (Kasim & Mura, 2022; Singh et al., 2023). Improved infrastructure and safety are essential for increasing tourism appeal and local satisfaction (Higgins & McLaughlin, 2020).

5.1.2 Tourism barriers in small towns of scenic areas.

The study identifies significant barriers to tourism development, including insufficient funding (mean = 2.6944), inadequate infrastructure (mean = 2.7222), and limited marketing efforts (mean = 2.7222). These barriers are consistent with the challenges highlighted in recent literature, which points to financial constraints and infrastructure deficits as major impediments to tourism growth (Adebayo et al., 2021; Bowers et al., 2022). Furthermore, the lack of adequate training for tourism professionals and safety concerns also align with previous findings that underscore the need for better investment and strategic planning to overcome these barriers (Johnson & Park, 2020; Lee & Murphy, 2023).

5.1.3 Tourism promotion strategies in small towns of scenic areas

The findings suggest moderate support for various tourism promotion strategies, including infrastructure investment (mean = 3.0278) and community-based initiatives (mean = 2.7778). Establishing eco-friendly accommodations and collaborating with local businesses received moderate to low support. These results reflect the recent emphasis on integrating sustainable practices and enhancing community involvement to improve tourism outcomes (Nguyen & Kaur, 2022; Zhao et al., 2023). Strategic marketing and responsible tourism practices also emerged as areas requiring further development, in line with current

recommendations for enhancing tourism visibility and sustainability (Clark & Smith, 2021; Wang & Zhang, 2022).

5.2 conclusions

Based on the study findings, a number of conclusions were made in line with the dimensions of the study as stated in chapter one;

The research finds a strong positive relationship between tourism status and small town development, with an R^2 value of 0.903 and a significant correlation coefficient of $r = 0.811$. This suggests that improvements in tourism infrastructure, promotion, and services significantly enhance the development and appeal of these towns. Effective tourism practices and management are vital for boosting the status and viability of small towns, highlighting the need for ongoing assessment and strategic improvements (Crouch & Ritchie, 1999; Weaver & Lawton, 2014).

Additionally, in line with the second dimension, the researcher concluded that the analysis reveals a highly significant positive correlation between perceived tourism barriers and the development of small towns ($r = 0.902$, $p < 0.01$), and the regression model supports this relationship with an R^2 of 0.740. This suggests that the more significant the barriers perceived in tourism, the greater the impact on the development of small towns. Addressing barriers such as insufficient funding, inadequate infrastructure, and limited marketing efforts is essential for fostering tourism growth and improving the attractiveness of these towns (Coleman, 2012; Page & Connell, 2006). By overcoming these barriers, towns can enhance their tourism potential and overall development.

The analysis shows a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.963$) and regression result ($R^2 = 0.568$) between effective tourism promotion strategies and the development of small towns. This indicates that improved promotion significantly enhances the appeal and growth of these towns. The results support the view that targeted marketing and strategic promotion are crucial for attracting tourists and boosting local economies (Kotler & Keller, 2016; Moutinho, 1987). Implementing robust promotion strategies, including community involvement and infrastructure investment, is essential for sustainable growth.

5.3 recommendations

There for, in line with the conclusions above, the following recommendations were made as per the study objectives;

5.3.1 Current Status of Tourism and Small Town Development

To leverage the positive impact of tourism on small town development, focus on enhancing tourism infrastructure by upgrading transportation, accommodation, and recreational facilities; promote strategic marketing with targeted campaigns and diverse media channels to showcase unique town attractions; and improve tourism services by training local businesses and service providers, and implementing feedback systems to elevate service quality.

5.3.2 Perceived Tourism Barriers and Town Development

To address barriers to tourism and enhance small town development, focus on increasing funding through various sources like government grants and private investments, upgrading essential infrastructure such as roads and public amenities, expanding marketing efforts with targeted advertising and travel influencers, and engaging stakeholders by fostering collaboration among local businesses, community organizations, and government agencies to collectively address and overcome challenges.

5.3.3 Effectiveness of Tourism Promotion Strategies

To maximize the impact of tourism promotion on town development, implement targeted approaches: develop robust campaigns highlighting the town's unique attractions using both traditional and digital media; actively involve local residents and businesses to ensure authenticity; partner with professional marketing agencies for expert guidance; and continuously monitor performance metrics, adapting strategies as needed to enhance effectiveness and respond to market changes.

5.4 Limitations of the study

The study faced several limitations, including the high transportation costs required to reach Sanga(C) ward and Sanga town council, the unavailability of busy employees who were engaged in other commitments, and difficulties in collecting data from respondents with limited formal education, which prolonged communication and data collection.

5.5. Areas of Further Research

This study has proven that tourism is beneficial when the national park is being well maintained and managed by the management, tourists and the local people there is therefore need for research regarding the development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas of Uganda.

References;

- African Nature Based Tourism Platform. (2022). *Country Summary Report: Uganda. January, 1–7.*
- Biswas, C. (2020). *INVESTIGATING BARRIERS IN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT : THE CASE OF BANGLADESH. August.*
- Donaldson, R., Spocter, M., Du Plessis, D., & Van Niekerk, A. (2012). Towards generic interventions to stimulate growth potential in small towns of the Western Cape Province, South Africa. *South African Geographical Journal, 94*(2), 120–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03736245.2012.742781>
- Duxbury, N., Silva, S., & de Castro, T. V. (2019). Creative Tourism Development in Small Cities and Rural Areas in Portugal: Insights from Start-Up Activities. *Creating and Managing Experiences in Cultural Tourism, 291–304.* https://doi.org/10.1142/9789813233683_0018
- East African Community. (2016). EAC Vision 2050: Regional vision for socio-economic transformation and development. *Group, February, 80.*
<http://www.wbcds.org/pages/edocument/edocumentdetails.aspx?id=219&nosearchcontextkey=true>
- English, P., & Ahebwa, W. M. (2019). *How can tourism become a driver of economic growth in Uganda? / International Growth Centre. November 2018.* <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32096.40967>
- Eun, E., Kim, K., & Mattila, A. S. (n.d.). *No Title.*
- Goodwin, H. (2008). Tourism, local economic development , and poverty reduction. *Applied Research in Economic Development, 5*(3), 55–64.
- He, Y. (2019). *Research on Planning and Design of Small Towns of Tourist Reception Type Based on Regional Culture Taking Jiugongshan Town, Tongshan County, Xianning as an Example. 310(Iccese), 416–422.* <https://doi.org/10.2991/iccese-19.2019.93>
- Ilollari, O. (2023). *The Trend of Tourism as a Driver of Economic Growth and the Policies to Develop it to a Sustainable Future in Albania. June.*
- Kaila, P. M. (2002). *TOURISM AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES IN RHODES : THE AWARENESS OF THE LOCAL.*
- Kantawateera, K., Naipinit, A., Sakolnakorn, T. P. N., & Kroeksakul, P. (2015). Tourist transportation problems and guidelines for developing the tourism industry in Khon Kaen, Thailand. *Asian Social Science, 11*(2), 89–95. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v11n2p89>
- King, A. P., Wanyana, M. W., Simbwa, B. N., Marrie, Z. G., Migisha, R., Kadobera, D., Kwesiga, B., Gonahasa, D., Ahabwe, P. B., Mayinja, H., Joyce, K., Itiakorit, H., Nchoko, S., Salat, E., Weithaka, F., Odhiambo, F., Vicent, M., Metuschelah, H., Alexis, M., ... Ario, A. (2023). *Quarterly Epidemiological Bulletin: April – June, 2023. 8*(2).
- Koc, E., Aydın, G., Ar, A. A., & Boz, H. (2017). Emotions and emotional abilities in service failures and recovery. In *Service failures and recovery in tourism and hospitality: a practical manual* (Issue October). <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781786390677.0042>
- Kwiatek-Sołtys, A., & Bajgier-Kowalska, M. (2019). The Role of Cultural Heritage Sites in the Creation of Tourism Potential of Small Towns in Poland. *European Spatial Research and Policy, 26*(2), 237–255.

<https://doi.org/10.18778/1231-1952.26.2.11>

LMNP. (n.d.).

Lu, R. (2022). *Sustainable Scenic Tourism: A Case Study of Changchun City, China*. 2(2), 75–85. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>

Majewska, A., Denis, M., Krzysztofik, S., & Monika Maria, C. P. (2022). The development of small towns and towns of well-being: Current trends, 30 years after the change in the political system, based on the Warsaw suburban area. *Land Use Policy*, 115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.105998>

Mohammed, M. R., Ibrahim, M., & Kawugana, A. (2021). The relationship of training cost , training needs and training selection criteria on staff performance of federal inland and revenue service. *Research Journal of Management Practice*, 1(20), 69–89.

MTWA Tourism Statistical Abstract 2024 26032024.pdf. (n.d.).

Muoki, D. (2021). Impact Assessment of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Tourism and Hospitality Industry in the EAC and Post Recovery Strategy for the Sector-Working Paper -. *Covid-19_018*, 64.

NDP. (2013). Uganda Vision 2040. *Annual Meeting of the Midwest Political Science ...*, 12(3), 1–7.

Okech, R. N. (2007). Local communities and management of heritage sites: Case study of Lamu Old Town. *Anatolia*, 18(2), 189–202. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13032917.2007.9687201>

Peeters, W., Dirix, J., & Sterckx, S. (2013). *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities : A Multi-Disciplinary Putting Sustainability into Sustainable Human Development Putting Sustainability into Sustainable Human Development*. March, 37–41.

Rahi, S. (2017). Research Design and Methods: A Systematic Review of Research Paradigms, Sampling Issues and Instruments Development. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*, 06(02). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2162-6359.1000403>

Ridho, Z., & Alisa, F. (2020). Sustainable Cultural Tourism Development: A Strategic For Revenue Generation in Local Communities. *Research Culture*, 4(2), 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.21428/e61c265e.f512dbd8>

Rogerson, C. M. (2016). Outside the cities: Tourism pathways in South Africa’s small towns and rural areas. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure SPECIAL EDITION*, 5(3), 1–16. <http://www.ajhtl.com>

Sadrija, T. L., & Desku, B. R. (2022). Tourism Capacity Management and Growth Trend. *Quality - Access to Success*, 23(189), 192–198. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/23.189.22>

Scheyvens, R., Banks, G., & Hughes, E. (2016). *The Private Sector and the SDGs: The Need to Move Beyond ‘ Business as Usual . ’* 382(March), 371–382. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.1623>

Schindler, O., & Cooper, O. (2014). *business Research methods*.

Selemon, B., Fakana, T., & Mengist, A. B. (2019). *Factors Hindering Tourism Industry Development: Gambella People’s National Regional State, South West Ethiopia*. 19(1).

- Shakur, O., & Alabi, R. A. (2018). Rural Tourism Development in Nigeria: Prospects and Challenges. *Afro Asian Journal of Social Sciences*, IX(I), 1–25.
- Shichiyakh, R. A. (2019). <http://jssidoi.org/esc/home>. 7(2), 1217–1229.
- Statistics, O. F., On, R., & Statistics, M. (2021). *UGANDA BUREAU OF STATISTICS REPORT ON MIGRATION STATISTICS YEAR 2020 January 2021*. January.
- Steinführer, A., Vaishar, A., & Zapletalová, J. (2016). The small town in rural areas as an underresearched type of settlement. editors' introduction to the special issue. *European Countryside*, 8(4), 322–332. <https://doi.org/10.1515/euco-2016-0023>
- Tessema, G. A., Poesen, J., Verstraeten, G., Van Rompaey, A., & Van Der Borg, J. (2021). The scenic beauty of geosites and its relation to their scientific value and geoscience knowledge of tourists: A case study from southeastern Spain. *Land*, 10(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land10050460>
- Thetsane, R. M. (2019). Local Community Participation in Tourism Development: The Case of Katse Villages in Lesotho. *Athens Journal of Tourism*, 6(2), 123–140. <https://doi.org/10.30958/ajt.6-2-4>
- Tyrrell, T., Paris, C. M., & Jr, V. B. (2012). *A Quantified Triple Bottom Line for Tourism : Experimental Results*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287512465963>
- UWA. (2021). *National Plan for Management of Wildlife Outside Uwa Protected Areas*. February. <http://www.ugandawildlife.org>
- World Travel and Tourism Council. (2021). Global Economic Impact & Trends 2021. *World Travel & Tourism Council*, 1–29. <https://wttc.org/Portals/0/Documents/Reports/2021/Global Economic Impact and Trends 2021.pdf>

APPENDICES;

APPENDIX I: Letter of introduction

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FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCES

Date: 22/07/2024

To: SANGA C/Man Baga...
SANGA TOWN COUNCIL
KIRUHURA DISTRICT

0702088103/cm

Dear Sir/Madam,

RE: DATA COLLECTION

On behalf of Busitema University, Faculty of Management Sciences, please allow me extend my appreciation to your organization for the continued support and commitment to providing services to our community. The Faculty looks forward to continuously partner with your organization in pursuance of excellence of our students by exposing them to practical learning experiences.

It's a University requirement that every student must carry out research and write a report in order to satisfy the requirement for the award of a Bachelor's Degree. The purpose of this letter is therefore to humbly request you to allow our fore mentioned student who is in Final year of study on a programme of Bachelors of Tourism and Travel Management of Busitema University, to carry out research by way of collecting data in your esteemed organization.

We look forward to your supportive and positive response to our request above.

Yours faithfully,

[Signature]
Jowalle Wampande
+256752566618; Wampande@BUSITEMA.UG
Ag. HOD (Tourism and Hospitality Mgt.)
HOD TOURISM & HOSPITALITY MGT
FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCES
29 MAY 2024
BUSITEMA UNIVERSITY
PO BOX 53, JINJA, UGANDA

APPENDIX II: QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire

Dear respondent,

My name is **Kusasira Emmanuel**, Registration number **BU/UG/2021/3404** an undergraduate student at Busitema University faculty of management sciences in Pallisa Uganda. As part of my studies, I am required to carry out field research and write a report on *“The development of tourism in small towns of scenic areas of Uganda using a case study of Sanga (C) Ward, Sanga Town Council, Kiruhura District near Lake Mburo National Park.”*

The research is for academic purposes and will not be used elsewhere other than for the purpose of a partial fulfillment for the award of a degree in tourism and travel management. You have been chosen as a respondent because of the knowledge and information that you have with regards to the topic. All the information provided will be treated with confidentiality.

Guidelines

Tick where appropriate

Information provided will be treated as confidential and will be used only for academic purpose only in order to complete the research work on the study topic.

For section B, C, D and E you're requested to tick one box per question and the answers are rated using a scale of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 with the different abbreviation of 5 (strongly Agree), 4(Agree), 3 (Not Sure), 2 (Strongly Disagree) and 1(Disagree) as quoted from section B to D.

SECTION A: PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Please tick the option that best describes you.

1. Gender

Male	Female

2. Position in the national or small towns

Tourists and visitors	Conservation department	Local businesses	Tour guides	Local community leaders in small towns

3. Educational qualifications

Certificate	Diploma certificate	Bachelor’s degree	Post graduate

4. Organizational (national park) period of existence

Less than 20 years	20-30 years	30 years and above years

5. Age of the respondents

18-25	26-35	36-45	46-55	55 and above

SECTION B: TOURISM CURRENT STATUS ASSESSMENT

To get your view on the Current status of tourism in small towns surrounding scenic area of Lake Mburo national park, please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement using a scale of 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Not sure), 2 (Disagree), 1 (Strongly Disagree) with the following statements;

S/N	Statements	1	2	3	4	5
CS1	Tourism in small towns surrounding Lake					

	Mburo is adequately promoted.					
CS2	The infrastructure in small towns surrounding Lake Mburo supports tourism activities effectively.					
CS3	Accommodation options in small towns surrounding Lake Mburo meet the needs of tourists.					
CS4	Small towns surrounding Lake Mburo offer a variety of tourist attractions and activities.					
CS5	Safety and security measures in small towns surrounding Lake Mburo are adequate for tourists.					
CS6	Local communities in small towns surrounding Lake Mburo actively participate in tourism development.					
CS7	Local businesses in small towns surrounding Lake Mburo actively engage with tourists.					

SECTION C: TOURISM BARRIERS

To get your view on Factors hindering the development of tourism in a developing country like Uganda, please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement using a scale of 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Not sure), 2 (Disagree), 1 (Strongly Disagree) with the following statements;

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
HF1	Insufficient funding allocated to tourism development projects in Uganda.					
HF2	Lack of adequate infrastructure (roads, airports, etc.) for tourism in Uganda.					
HF3	Limited marketing and promotion efforts for					

	Ugandan tourist destinations.					
HF4	Inadequate training and education programs for tourism professionals in Uganda.					
HF5	Lack of safety and security measures for tourists in Uganda.					
HF6	Limited access to financing and investment opportunities for tourism entrepreneurs in Uganda.					
HF7	Cultural misunderstandings and conflicts affecting tourism experiences in Uganda.					

SECTION D: TOURISM PROMOTION STRATEGIES

To get your view on strategies for promoting tourism and sustainable development in small towns surrounding Lake Mbuoro national park, please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement using a scale of 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Not sure), 2 (Disagree), 1 (Strongly Disagree) with the following statements;

S/N	Statements	1	2	3	4	5
SP1	Implementing community-based tourism initiatives to involve local residents in tourism development.					
SP2	Investing in infrastructure improvement projects (roads, signage, and facilities) in small towns surrounding Lake Mbuoro National Park.					
SP3	Establishing eco-friendly accommodation options in the small towns surrounding Lake Mbuoro National Park.					
SP4	Collaborating with local businesses to offer authentic and unique tourist experiences.					
SP5	Enhancing safety and security measures for tourists in the small towns surrounding Lake Mbuoro National Park.					
SP6	Encouraging responsible tourism practices through education and awareness campaigns.					
SP7	Implementing marketing and promotional campaigns to attract more visitors to the small towns surrounding Lake Mbuoro National Park.					

SECTION E: SMALL TOWNS IN SCENIC AREAS

To get your view on small towns in scenic areas, please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement using a scale of 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Not sure), 2 (Disagree), 1 (Strongly Disagree) with the following statements;

S/N	Statements	1	2	3	4	5
ST1	Tourism development in small towns of scenic areas, like those near Lake Mbuoro National Park, significantly contributes to local economic growth.					
ST2	The presence of scenic attractions in small towns, such as Lake Mbuoro National Park, attracts tourists and stimulates business activities in the area.					
ST3	Investments in tourism infrastructure and amenities in small towns near scenic areas are essential for attracting and accommodating tourists.					
ST4	Collaborative efforts between local communities, government agencies, and tourism stakeholders are crucial for sustainable tourism development in small towns.					
ST5	Cultural and environmental conservation efforts in small towns near scenic areas play a significant role in enhancing the overall tourism experience.					
ST6	The promotion of ecotourism activities in small towns near scenic areas, such as those around Lake Mbuoro National Park, helps to attract responsible tourists.					
ST7	Improved accessibility and transportation					

	infrastructure to small towns near scenic areas are necessary to support tourism development in these regions.					
ST8	Effective marketing strategies highlighting the unique attractions of small towns near scenic areas, like Lake Mburu National Park, are vital for tourism growth.					
ST9	Sustainable tourism practices, including waste management and conservation initiatives, are crucial for preserving the natural beauty of small towns near scenic areas.					
ST10	The development of diverse tourism offerings, beyond wildlife viewing, in small towns near scenic areas enhances visitor satisfaction and encourages longer stays.					

THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME AND PARTICIPATION

APPENDIX III: Work plan for 2024.

Activity	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST
Proposal writing				
Proposal defense				
Data collection				
Research writing				
Submitting the research				

APPENDIX IV: RESEARCH BUDGET

ITEM	QTY	PRICE	AMOUNT(UGX)
Stationary	1	20000	20000
Travelling	2 trips	100000	200000
Research assistants	2	30000	60000
Typing of work	4 times	3500	14000
Data collection	6 days	10000	60000
Printing and binding	59 pages (3 copies)	200	64000
Grand total	-	-	364,000

APPENDIX VI: KREJCIE AND MORGAN (1970) TABLE

<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>
10	10	220	140	1200	291
15	14	230	144	1300	297
20	19	240	148	1400	302
25	24	250	152	1500	306
30	28	260	155	1600	310
35	32	270	159	1700	313
40	36	280	162	1800	317
45	40	290	165	1900	320
50	44	300	169	2000	322
55	48	320	175	2200	327
60	52	340	181	2400	331
65	56	360	186	2600	335
70	59	380	191	2800	338
75	63	400	196	3000	341
80	66	420	201	3500	346
85	70	440	205	4000	351
90	73	460	210	4500	354
95	76	480	214	5000	357
100	80	500	217	6000	361
110	86	550	226	7000	364
120	92	600	234	8000	367
130	97	650	242	9000	368
140	103	700	248	10000	370
150	108	750	254	15000	375
160	113	800	260	20000	377
170	118	850	265	30000	379
180	123	900	269	40000	380
190	127	950	274	50000	381
200	132	1000	278	75000	382
210	136	1100	285	100000	384

Note.—*N* is population size. *S* is sample size.

Source: Krejcie & Morgan, 1970